

Dissemination: Share confidently

Publish & Reuse

Connect Scholarly Products

Consider ways to link access of your research outputs with persistent identifiers (PIDs). A PID is a long-lasting digital reference to a contributor, organization, or object.

- **People:** [Open Researcher and Contributor ID](#) (ORCID) is an alphanumeric code to uniquely identify scientific and other academic authors and contributors. ORCIDs can be linked to many other profiles.
- **Organizations:** [Research Organization Registry](#) (ROR) aims to provide a persistent identifier for every research organization in the world.
- **Works:** [Digital Object Identifier](#) (DOI) is a persistent identifier or handle used to uniquely identify various objects, including articles, conference proceedings, datasets, research materials, etc.
- **Resources:** [Research Resource Identifiers](#) (RRID) help researchers cite key resources, including antibodies, model organisms, cell lines, plasmids, software tools, and databases.

Select Appropriate Data Repository(ies)

[Data repositories](#) are the preferred method for sharing because they support the discovery, access, and long-term availability of data. Choose the appropriate repository(ies) for all your data types.

- **[Domain-Specific Repository](#):** Have a specific focus, either by data type or by biomedical research discipline. These are good first choices for your data. Examples: NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO), NCBI Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP), NIMH Data Archive (NDA).
- **[Generalist Repository](#):** Accept data regardless of data type, discipline, or affiliation. These may be used when there isn't an established repository for your data, or you need to share more general data or materials. Examples: Open Science Framework, figshare, Zenodo, Vivli.
- **[Institutional Repository](#):** Focused on preserving and disseminating the scholarship produced by the institution's faculty and students. Example: [Harvard Dataverse](#)

★ Follow the [Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative \(GREI\)](#)

GREI brings together seven NIH-recognized platforms for sharing NIH-funded research data. Harvard provides support for three of these recognized platforms: [Harvard Dataverse](#), [Open Science Framework](#), and [Vivli](#). Utilize the comparison and flow charts to determine the best generalist repository for your research data.

Confirm FAIR Data Principles

To advance science efficiently and ensure reproducibility, follow the [FAIR Data Principles](#):

- **Findable:** Make sure your data can be found – by both humans and search engines.
 - Use repositories to make data searchable and discoverable online, provide structured metadata descriptions, and assign a unique and persistent identifier (e.g., DOI).
- **Accessible:** Tell – both humans and machines – how they can get access to your data.
 - Most published research data is open and available for immediate download. If data cannot be open (e.g., because it contains sensitive information), describe the restrictions and how to request access.
- **Interoperable:** Ensure your data can be integrated with other data and utilized by applications.
 - Avoid sharing proprietary files, using open formats to facilitate easy access and reuse. Use controlled vocabularies and well-defined models to ensure data are well-structured.
- **Reusable:** Make sure data – and related metadata – are well-described.
 - Provide documentation at both the study level and file level. Remove ambiguity about what others can and can't do with your data by assigning a license (e.g., [Creative Commons Zero](#)), and provide a citation to make it easier for others to cite your work.